

Role of Capital Market Achieving SDGs (G-9; Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) for Developing Country by 2030: Bangladesh Perspective

24 September, 2019

Submitted by:

Md. Zafar Iqbal ndc

(Additional Secretary to the Govt.)

Member Directing Staff (M&D)

Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre

Savar, Dhaka-1343

Md. Edrich Molla

(Researcher of Finance, Jagannath University)

Assistant Professor

Department of Business Administration

Victoria University of Bangladesh

Panthapath, Dhaka-1205

Submitted to:

Deputy Director (Research)

Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre

Savar, Dhaka-1343

Bangladesh

Role of Capital Market Achieving SDGs (G-9; Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) for Developing Country by 2030: Bangladesh Perspective

INTRODUCTION

The capital market plays an important role in economic development of Bangladesh. Capital market in Bangladesh consists of two full-fledged automated stock exchanges- the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) and the Chittagong Stock Exchange (CSE). Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC), as the supervisory body regulates the stock exchanges of the country. Though capital market plays significant role in economic development by channeling long term funds from savers to investors, capital market in Bangladesh is still lagging behind as compared to those of South Asian and South-east Asian countries. Banks play dominant roles in financing economic activities in Bangladesh. However, banks are not in a position to finance a long term productive investment activities continuously following higher level of non-performing loan and risk of maturity mismatch of funds. Given this, Bangladesh needs to undertake measures to expand capital market for financing productive investments and infrastructural projects. To this end, regulator of capital market BSEC may undertake some pragmatic steps to ensure good corporate governance motivate good companies for floating bonds, shares and continue legal facilitation with more attractive incentives, especially for the foreign participants.

The United Nations sets 17 (Seventeen) sustainable development goals (SDGs) achieving by 2030 to transform the globe such goals are; no poverty, zero hunger, good health and well-being, quality education, gender equality, clean water and sanitation, affordable and clean energy, decent work and economic growth, industry, innovation and infrastructure, reduced inequality, sustainable cities and communities, responsible consumption and production, climate action, life below water, life on land, peace and justice strong institutions and finally partnerships to achieve the goal. In this study researchers will focus on goal number 9 (nine) i.e. **industry, innovation and infrastructure** for the economic development of Bangladesh.

Source: Department of economic and social affairs disability, the United Nations

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this part a number of scholars' published articles, research papers, thesis paper, project reports and websites will be studied and cited. Following are the related literatures which have been reviewed preliminarily for this study:

According to Demirguc-Kunt, Asli (1992), only as development proceeds further do the financial markets become more sophisticated. In the recent years stock markets started emerging in a number of developing countries. Although it is widely known that an increase

in the variety and magnitude of financial institutions and services would improve the allocation of saving and investment, there is skepticism about the role these emerging markets play in developing countries. **Merton, Robert C (1992)** found that developing country stock markets are criticized for being purely speculative. In other words, it is claimed that the observed prices and their volatility cannot be explained by their underlying fundamentals, leading to adverse real effects for capital formation and welfare. It is also argued that market discipline cannot be established in developing countries due to information disclosure problems, costly monitoring and enforcement mechanisms, and lack of sufficient number of informed investors, all of which exacerbate the usual asymmetric information and moral hazard problems. Another criticism is directed towards the stock markets' potential for destabilizing developing countries' financial system by allowing rapid inflows and outflows of capital, merely reflecting the perceptions of international investors. **Fase, Martin MG et al. (2003)** found financial development matters for economic growth and that causality run from financial structure to economic development. This result indicated that in developing countries a policy of financial reform was likely to improve economic growth. **Mishkin, Frederic S. (1996)** described that the financial system has an extremely important function in the economy because it enables funds to move from economic agents who lack productive investment opportunities to those who have such opportunities. Unless the financial system can do this job effectively, the economy will not function efficiently and economic growth will be severely hampered. **Reisen, Helmut et al. (2001)** aimed at the growth impact of private capital (in)flows. Some Asian countries have been blamed for discouraging long-term equity inflows and encouraging short-term inflows in the past. Thus, particular effort will be made to provide evidence on the independent growth impact that the various broad categories of net capital inflows are likely to exert.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In this part of the study mainly will be focused on finding relationship between capital market and SDGs-2030 (G-9; Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) for developing country in the context of Bangladesh.

Figure: Self-developed Model on SDG Framework

Problem Statement

While conducting this research it may be experienced insufficient secondary data since a few numbers of researches have been conducted by the researchers in the past in this field. Besides, it is too difficult for the researchers to collect primary data from different stakeholders like government departments, brokerage houses as well as individuals.

Rationale of the Study

The capital market is the market for long-term loans and equity capital. Developing countries in fact, view capital market as the engine for future growth through mobilizing of surplus fund to the deficit group. An efficient capital market may perform as an alternative to many other financing sources as being the least cost capital source. Especially in a country like ours, where savings is minimal, and capital market can no wonder be a lucrative source of finance. At times when the banking sector of the country is facing the challenge of bringing down the advance deposit ratio to sustainable level, the economy of the country is unfolding newer horizon of opportunities. Due to over-exposure level of the financial system the securities market could play a very positive role, had there been no market debacle.

The capital market also helps increase savings and investment, which are essential for economic development. A Stock market, by allowing diversification across a variety of assets, helps to reduce the risk of the investors must bear, thus reducing the cost of capital, which in turn spurs investment and economic growth. From the above points it is easily realize that capital market is the most important sector to accumulate capital for the industrialization of the country, but it is most vulnerable. For that, we have motivated to dig deep into these issues and accordingly we have under taken the study to evaluate the performance of the capital market for achieving SDG. The study is an endeavor that will be helpful to the listed companies, stock brokers, Management of DSE, CSE, SEC, and Bangladesh Government.

Research Questions

In this study there will be three specific research questions which will be observed, analyzed and discussed. The specific questions are:

1. Is there any significant relationship between capital market and industrial development for sustainable development of a country?
2. Is there any significant relationship between capital market and innovation for sustainable development of a country?
3. Is there any significant relationship between capital market and infrastructural development for sustainable development of a country?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the paper is to ascertain the impact of capital market on the economic development of Bangladesh. More specifically the main aim of this study is to evaluate capital market performance of the DSE and CSE, highlight its growth and development, analyze the performance of securities listed and examine the market capitalization as well as the contribution to GDP of the country. It transfers the fund from surplus units to deficit units for investment. The specific purpose of the study is to examine the significance of stock market in sustainable economic development of Bangladesh.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This study will be confined to find out the relationship between capital market and SDGs-2030 (G-9; Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) for developing country in the context of Bangladesh. Mixed (both quantitative and qualitative) research method will be adopted to collect secondary data. Stakeholders of both Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) and Chittagong Stock Exchange (CSE) will be considered as target population of this research. Random sampling technique will be used to collect data and information for the analyses. Proposed 140 (one hundred and forty) individual and institutional stakeholders of the capital market will be considered as sample size. Primary and secondary sources will be considered to collect data and information to conduct this study. Secondary data and information will be collected from different reports, books, journal articles, newspapers and authentic online sources. Conversely primary data will be collected through structured questionnaire. Besides, focused group discussion and in depth interview will be conducted as per requirements.

The collected data from both primary and secondary sources will be observed, analyzed using statistical tools i.e. discrete statistics, correlation analysis, time series analysis and other necessary research applications in SPSS and Microsoft Excel software. After analyzing the data and information results and findings will be presented in the form of table, pie chart, histogram, percentage and other logical ways if requires.

Ethical Issues During and After Fieldwork

The basic rule in any research field is causing no harm to any of the research participants including the principal researcher, informants and other field assistants. In order to carry out field work in such settings, ethical issues of personal security should be considered from the very beginning when developing research design and methods. In order to avoid probable bias, attempts will be made to maintain a level of objectivity at all stages of the research. We shall be well aware of potential bias before conducting fieldwork. To avoid possible data distortion, all the interviews will be recorded with the permission of the interviewees. To follow the research ethics, permission will be granted before taking pictures.

We shall assure the respondents that we shall not reveal their names neither in any newspaper nor in my research paper. We shall also assure them that their symbolic names may be used for research purpose. But for research ethics, we shall prefer not to mention any names of the research participants while writing our research report.

EFERENCES

1. Demirguc-Kunt, Asli. Developing country capital structures and emerging stock markets. World Bank, 1992.
2. Fase, Martin MG, and R. C. N. Abma. "Financial environment and economic growth in selected Asian countries." *Journal of Asian economics* 14, no. 1 (2003): 11-21.
3. <https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/about-us/sustainable-development-goals-sdgs-and-disability.html>
4. Merton, Robert C. "Financial innovation and economic performance." *Journal of applied corporate finance* 4, no. 4 (1992): 12-22.
5. Mishkin, Frederic S. *Understanding financial crises: a developing country perspective*. No. w5600. National Bureau of Economic Research, 1996.
6. Reisen, Helmut, and Marcelo Soto. "Which types of capital inflows foster developing-country growth?" *International finance* 4, no. 1 (2001): 1-14.